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A Gaussian wake model for Airborne Wind Energy Systems

Filippo Trevisi, Lorenzo Jr Sabug and Lorenzo Fagiano

Department of Electronics, Information and Bioengineering, Politecnico di Milano, Piazza Leonardo da Vinci 32, 20133 Milano, Italy

E-mail: filippo.trevisi@polimi.it

Abstract. Modeling the aerodynamic interactions between Airborne Wind Energy Systems (AWES) is an open and challenging problem. To this end, a new Gaussian wake model is introduced for fly-gen AWES, also called windplanes here. The engineering wake models of windplanes can be split in induction models, used to find the induced velocities at the wing, and wake models, used to account for the wind deficit downwind. The proposed model combines an improved induction model, starting from one available in the literature, with a novel wake model that assumes that the wake velocity has a Gaussian shape and imposes momentum conservation. The variance of the Gaussian wake is assumed to vary with the downstream distance from the windplane. The model entails just one tuning parameter that is estimated using CFD results from the literature, showing high accuracy. The new model is then used to study the influence of an upwind system on a downwind one. A sensitivity analysis is carried out by moving the downwind system in the direction transverse to the wind speed or by yawing it with respect to the wind direction. A maximum in power production of the downwind system is found when the projections of the two trajectories are partially overlapping. The extremely low computational cost of the model and the physical insights provided by this paper contribute to clear the way for simulation, planning and control of large scale airborne wind farms.

1. Introduction

Fly-gen Airborne Wind Energy Systems (AWES), also called windplanes in this paper, harvest wind power by means of small wind turbines, mounted onboard of an autonomous tethered aircraft that performs periodic quasi-circular trajectories roughly perpendicular to the wind (crosswind conditions, see Fig. 1). Electric power is generated onboard and transmitted to the ground via the tether [1]. AWES have the potential to significantly reduce the material use (approx 90% reduction) for the same power ratings of a conventional turbine, and thus reduce the cost of energy [2]. The most notable prototypes of fly-gen AWES were developed by Makani Power, which stopped operations in 2020 [3]. Their prototype featured an high aspect ratio wing and unconventional airfoils. Recently, a new design methodology was published, finding that windplanes with low aspect ratio and conventional efficient airfoils are optimal under the considered modeling assumptions [4]. This last design is used in the present study.

The long term success of AWES depends on the techno-economic scalability of the concept, among other factors. The technological scalability consists in increasing the windplane size and in adding multiple systems in a wind farm. Among various other aspects, it will be crucial to understand the wakes' interactions among systems in the farm, a subject which is not much explored yet in the literature. On the high fidelity side, a framework modeling the turbulent flow condition with large-eddy simulations (LES) and performing the flight path generation and tracking with optimal control techniques is used to study large scale airborne wind energy farms [5], finding relevant wake losses for dense fly-gen AWES farms. Such models are however rather costly computationally, thus difficult to implement and use in early-stage analyses and system

dimensioning, or for control development and initial testing. To this end, the main contribution of this paper is the development and analysis of a new, comprehensive wake model with low computational requirements. Referring to Fig. 1, the windplane wake develops along the axial (z) and the tangential (x) direction. This paper mainly analyzes the development of the wake in the axial direction to study the reduction in wind speed felt by a downwind system. The wake development in the tangential direction is due to the turbines, the wing and the tether, as shown in Fig. 1(c). The engineering model of the aerodynamic wake of windplanes can be split in two sub-problems:

- **The induction:** This is the problem of evaluating the induced velocities at the wing. Gaunaa et al. [6] first pointed out that momentum methods do not work for windplanes because significant inner and outer tip corrections are needed to take into account that the wind harvesting device is just one lifting line and not a uniformly distributed load over the annulus. They then introduce a vortex based model. Later, Trevisi et al. [7] derive a vortex model, based on vortex rings, which is summarized and improved in Sect. 2.
- **The wake:** This is the problem of evaluating the wind deficit after the wing. This problem is approached in the literature by assuming that the wake has a uniform reduction in wind speed (similar to the top-hat wake models for conventional wind turbines) inside an annular shaped wake [8, 9, 10]. The wind deficit and the annular region borders are estimated with momentum and mass conservation and the entrainment hypothesis. These models focus on the prediction of the uniform wind speed deficit, without estimating the wake effect on a downwind system. Our new model to compute the wind deficit after the windplane is proposed in Sect. 3. It is based on the assumption of a Gaussian annular wind deficit distribution, similar to what has been proposed for conventional turbines in [11, 12], and the effect on a downwind system is evaluated in Sect. 5.

This paper is meant to advance the development of low fidelity engineering models, by coupling a vortex-based induction model (Sect. 2) to a new Gaussian wake model (Sect. 3), by comparing the new model with CFD results (Sect. 4) and by evaluating the wake losses on a downwind system (Sect. 5).

2. The induction model

The windplane model used in this study is the one-degree-of-freedom model presented in [13], and the main equations recalled here. In this first study, fully crosswind operation is considered, while windplanes flying with non-zero average elevation above the ground will be considered in future works. The shaft power can be estimated with respect to the total onboard turbines area A_t , the onboard turbine power coefficient $C_{P,t}$ and the windplane tangential velocity u , which corresponds to the apparent velocity to the onboard turbines (Fig. 1),

$$P = \frac{1}{2} \rho A_t C_{P,t} u^3. \quad (1)$$

The power coefficient is defined as the ratio between the shaft power and the wind power passing through a disk with radius equal to the wingspan $A_{\text{ref}} = \pi b^2$ [4]

$$C_P = \frac{P}{\frac{1}{2} \rho \pi b^2 v_\infty^3} = C_{P,t} \underbrace{\frac{\xi_t^2}{2}}_{A_t/A_{\text{ref}}} \lambda^3, \quad (2)$$

where two onboard turbines with normalized radius $\xi_t = \frac{R_t}{b/2}$ (R_t is the actual radius) are assumed and the wing speed ratio is $\lambda = \frac{u}{v_\infty}$, with v_∞ being the free stream velocity.

The thrust coefficient C_T is defined as the scalar product of the aerodynamic force \mathbf{F}_a with the wind velocity \mathbf{v}_∞ , normalized with the wind power passing through A_{ref}

$$C_T = \frac{\mathbf{F}_a \cdot \mathbf{v}_\infty}{\frac{1}{2} \rho A_{\text{ref}} v_\infty^3} \approx \frac{L}{\frac{1}{2} \rho \pi b^2 v_\infty^2} = \frac{C_L}{\pi \mathcal{R}} \lambda^2, \quad (3)$$

Figure 1: Left and right rolled-up trailed helicoidal vortices **(a)** and relative modeling after assumptions **(b)** [7]. Velocity triangle, force balance and main wake components **(c)**.

where L is the aerodynamic lift, C_L the wing lift coefficient and \mathcal{R} the wing aspect ratio.

Assuming a steady crosswind motion, the net tangential force balance is null, as the propulsive lift is balanced by the parasite drag D_p and the turbine thrust T_t (see Fig. 1(c)). The wing speed ratio is then

$$\lambda = \frac{u}{v_\infty} = \frac{L(1-a)}{D_p + T_t} = \frac{C_L(1-a)}{C_{D,p} + \frac{\pi}{2} \mathcal{R} \xi_t^2 C_{T,t}}, \quad (4)$$

where a is the aerodynamic induction at the wing, $C_{D,p}$ is the aerodynamic parasite drag coefficient, inclusive of the airfoil drag and the tether drag, and $C_{T,t}$ is the onboard turbines thrust coefficient [4].

Assuming large turning radius $\kappa_0^2 = \left(\frac{b/2}{R_0}\right)^2 \ll 1$ and large wing speed ratios $\lambda^2 \gg 1$, the aerodynamic induction a generated by the helical vortex system (Fig. 1(a)) can be modeled as the sum of two terms: one due to the first half rotation of the helicoidal vortex filaments (the near wake induction a_n) and one related to the semi-infinite cascade of vortex rings (the far wake induction a_f) as in Fig. 1(b) [7]. The near wake induction, or the near wake induced drag, can be computed by assuming straight semi-infinite trailed vortices. The far wake induction can be instead computed as

$$a_f \approx \frac{9}{8\pi} \frac{\Gamma_0}{y_v v_\infty} \left(\frac{y_v}{R_0}\right)^{\pi/2} \left(\frac{\lambda_0}{2\pi}\right)^{3/2}, \quad (5)$$

where Γ_0 is the tip vortex strength, y_v is its spanwise position and λ_0 is the normalized torsional parameter of the helicoidal wake. λ_0 can be estimated from the wake pitch h_0

$$h_0 = v_\infty (1 - a_r) \frac{2\pi R_0}{u}, \quad (6)$$

where $v_\infty (1 - a_r)$ is the axial velocity of the vortex rings. Gaunaa et al. [6] evaluate the helix pitch h_0 by modeling the vortex rings as infinite straight vortices. With this modeling, the

convection velocity of the rings, assuming that the dominant effect in the motion of the tip vortices is the vorticity of the nearest tip vortex, is

$$a_r = \frac{1}{v_\infty} \frac{\Gamma_0}{2\pi(2y_v)}, \quad (7)$$

Assuming an elliptic wing loading and neglecting the influence of the turbines, $\Gamma_0 = 2v_\infty b \frac{C_L}{\pi R} \lambda$ and $y_v = \frac{\pi}{8} b$ [6]. The normalized torsional parameter λ_0 is then

$$\lambda_0 = \frac{2\pi R_0}{h_0} = \frac{\lambda}{1 - a_r} = \frac{\lambda}{1 - \frac{4}{\pi^2} \frac{C_T}{\lambda}}. \quad (8)$$

Note that in this work we use the closure model in Eq. (8), instead of the closure models proposed by Trevisi et al. [7], because its derivation has a better physical explanation and indeed performs better for the analyzed cases (Sect. 4).

The turning radius R_0 , needed to evaluate the inverse turning ratio $\kappa_0 = \frac{b/2}{R_0}$, can be estimated by setting the centrifugal force $m \frac{u^2}{R_0}$ equal to the radial component of the tether force $T \tan(\Phi)$ (see Fig. 1(c))[4]. The opening angle Φ is then

$$\sin \Phi \tan \Phi = \frac{m}{\frac{1}{2} \rho A C_L L_{te}}, \quad (9)$$

where A is the wing area, L_{te} is the tether length and the turning radius is $R_0 = L_{te} \sin \Phi$.

3. The wake deficit model

In this section, a new Gaussian wake model is derived. The induction in the wake is defined as

$$a_w = \frac{v_\infty - v_w}{v_\infty} = 1 - \frac{v_w}{v_\infty}, \quad (10)$$

where v_w is the velocity in the wake. Applying momentum conservation and neglecting viscous and pressure terms, the distribution of mean velocities should fulfill [14]

$$\rho \int_0^\infty v_w (v_\infty - v_w) dA = T. \quad (11)$$

By expressing the velocities in the wake as induction a_w and applying the thrust coefficient definition in Eq. (3), Eq. (11) can be written as

$$\int_0^\infty 2a_w (1 - a_w) d\tilde{A} = C_T, \quad (12)$$

where $\tilde{A} = \frac{\pi r^2}{\pi b^2}$, with r being the radial coordinate from the trajectory center. Similarly to the derivation of the Gaussian [11] and double Gaussian [12] wake models for wind turbines, we consider the induction in the wake with the form

$$a_w = a_w^*(z) f(r, \sigma(z)) = a_w^* e^{-\frac{(\tilde{A} - \tilde{A}_0)^2}{2\sigma^2}}, \quad (13)$$

where the Gaussian curve is parametrized with respect to the normalized area $\tilde{A} = \frac{\pi r^2}{\pi b^2}$ and not to the radius r , as done in [11, 12]. This parametrization of the Gaussian wake simplifies the derivation of the wake model, as the integral in Eq. (12) can be solved analytically:

$$\sqrt{2} a_w^{*2}(z) \sigma(z) \left(1 + \operatorname{erf} \left(\frac{\tilde{A}_0}{\sigma(z)} \right) \right) - \sqrt{2\pi} a_w^*(z) \sigma(z) \left(1 + \operatorname{erf} \left(\frac{\tilde{A}_0}{\sqrt{2} \sigma(z)} \right) \right) + C_T = 0, \quad (14)$$

where erf is the error function. The mean normalized area to be used in Eq. (13) is taken to be the normalized area associated to the turning radius $\tilde{A}_0 = \frac{\pi R_0^2}{\pi b^2} = 1/(4\kappa_0^2)$. We model the initial value of the induction at the wake center $a_w^*(z=0)$ to be equal to the mean wake induction in the far wake computed with 1D momentum theory \bar{a}_w . According to 1D momentum theory [10], the thrust can be expressed in terms of a constant induction \bar{a}_w as

$$\underbrace{\frac{1}{2}\rho C_T \pi b^2 v_\infty^2}_T = \frac{1}{2}\rho \left(4\frac{\bar{a}_w}{2} \left(1 - \frac{\bar{a}_w}{2}\right)\right) \underbrace{2\pi R_0 b}_{\text{swept area}} v_\infty^2 = \rho \bar{a}_w (2 - \bar{a}_w) \pi R_0 b v_\infty^2, \quad (15)$$

where \bar{a}_w in this formulation represents the induction in the far wake (and not in the rotation plane). The induction at the wake center can be then expressed as

$$a_w^*(z=0) = \bar{a}_w = 1 - \sqrt{1 - C_T \kappa_0}, \quad (16)$$

Eq. (14) can then be solved numerically to find the unknown variance $\sigma(z=0)$ which respects the momentum conservation in the wake. An approximate solution, which can be used as initial guess for solving Eq. (14) and can be obtained by considering $\text{erf}\left(\frac{\tilde{A}_0}{\sigma}\right) = \text{erf}\left(\frac{\tilde{A}_0}{\sqrt{2}\sigma}\right) = 1$, is $\sigma \approx \frac{C_T}{2\sqrt{2}(a_w^* \sqrt{\pi - a_w^{*2}})}$. Following the assumptions in [11, 12], the variance $\sigma(z)$ is modeled here to vary with the axial distance $\tilde{z} = \frac{z}{R_0}$ as

$$\sigma(z) = k^* \tilde{z} + \sigma(z=0), \quad (17)$$

where k^* is a parameter found by fitting experiments or CFD. Since, to the best of our knowledge, there is neither a theory nor an experiment regarding annular-shaped obstacles, a linear dependence of σ with respect to \tilde{z} is here considered. For a given $\sigma(z)$, the Gaussian amplitude $a_w^*(z)$, which satisfies the momentum conservation, can be found analytically as

$$a_w^*(z) = \frac{\sqrt{\pi} \left(1 + \text{erf}\left(\frac{\tilde{A}_0}{\sqrt{2}\sigma(z)}\right)\right) - \sqrt{\pi} \left(1 + \text{erf}\left(\frac{\tilde{A}_0}{\sqrt{2}\sigma(z)}\right)\right)^2 - 2\sqrt{2} \left(1 + \text{erf}\left(\frac{\tilde{A}_0}{\sigma(z)}\right)\right) \frac{C_T}{\sigma(z)}}{2 \left(1 + \text{erf}\left(\frac{\tilde{A}_0}{\sigma(z)}\right)\right)}. \quad (18)$$

4. Comparison with CFD

Given the early stages of development of Airborne Wind Energy, no experimental data of the aerodynamic wake of airborne wind energy systems are available, and neither are wind tunnel tests of annual shaped obstacles. We then carry out a comparison with CFD data. We use the simulations carried out by Kheiri et al. [9], which solve the unsteady Reynolds averaged Navier-Stokes equations closed by the $k - \omega$ SST turbulence model with ANSYS Fluent. The CFD analyses pertain to a rectangular wing with wingspan $b = 52.94$ m, aspect ratio of $\mathcal{R} = 14.5$ and Clark Y airfoils. The wing speed ratio is $\lambda = 10.92$, the inverse turning radius $\kappa_0 = 0.21$ and the thrust coefficient is $C_T = 2.02$. The turbulence intensity at the inlet is 1%. The same setup is also simulated with the vortex particle method implemented in DUST [15]. Since this code cannot resolve turbulence, it is used to validate the initial wake shape and the convention velocity of the vortex rings. The wing in DUST is modeled with vortex lattice elements, with 10 elements in the chord direction and 40 elements spanwise. The simulation is run for 25 revolutions, with a time-step each 5° .

Referring to Fig. 2, the average wind deficit distribution, computed with the different methods, is shown at different downwind location. The parameter in Eq. (17) is chosen as $k^* = 1/4$. The DUST results are shown for the correct downwind location and in the far wake (obtained at $\tilde{z} = \frac{z}{R_0} = 6$). The velocity distribution obtained with the continuity-momentum

Figure 2: Normalized wind speed as a function of the radial coordinate for increasing downstream positions $\tilde{z} = z/R_0$ computed with CFD [9], with the new Gaussian model, with the continuity-momentum wake model (CMW) [8] and with DUST [15] (vortex particle method).

wake model (CMW) is also shown, considering the parameters $\alpha = 0.058$, $\beta = 0.091$, $\xi^* = 7$ and $k = 2$ [8]. Overall the Gaussian wake model captures well the CFD trend, with a significant overestimation of the induction a_w in the inner part of the wake (i.e. toward $\tilde{r} \rightarrow 0$).

We use the DUST simulations to verify the assumption of the vortex filament convection velocity (Eq. 7). With this regards, Fig. 3a shows the contour plot of the axial velocity of a simulation with the inputs data from Kheiri et al. [9], while Fig. 3b with the inputs data from the case study analyzed in this paper. As we experience convergence issues with elliptic wings in DUST, Fig. 3b shows the solution for a trapezoidal wing planform with taper ratio of 0.5. A detailed analysis on the influence of the wing planform on the vortex rings position is left for future works. The model from Gaunaa et al. [6] better predicts the position of the vortex filaments, especially for the case study, which has a lower aspect ratio.

(a) Input data from Kheiri et al. [9].

(b) Input data from Table 1.

Figure 3: Contour plot of the axial velocity field computed with DUST and vortex rings position predicted by the implicit [7] (red lines) and by the Gaunaa model [6] (black lines).

5. Preliminary analyses for wind farm planning and control

In this section, we perform a preliminary study of the aerodynamic interaction between two windplanes. We consider an upwind system **up** flying fully crosswind in steady state, hence we neglect gravity. The downwind system **dn** is however facing a spatial-dependent wind field, so that the dynamic solution is unsteady, but periodic. Neglecting gravity, the tangential equation of motion is then

$$m\dot{u} = \underbrace{\frac{1}{2}\rho A C_L (u + v_{w,1})v_{w,3}(1 - a)}_{\text{propulsive lift}} - \underbrace{\frac{1}{2}\rho A C_{D,p}(u + v_{w,1})^2}_{\text{parasite drag}} - \underbrace{\frac{1}{2}\rho A_t C_{T,t}(u + v_{w,1})^2}_{\text{turbines thrust}}, \quad (19)$$

where \dot{u} is the tangential acceleration, $v_{w,1}$ and $v_{w,3}$ are the wind velocity, including the wake of the upwind system, along the tangential and axial direction. This equation of motion is solved for the periodic steady state within an optimal control framework, which employs an harmonic balance method [4]. The control inputs are the wing lift coefficient C_L and the onboard turbines induction a_t , which determines the onboard turbines thrust $C_{T,t}$ and power coefficient $C_{P,t}$ via 1D momentum theory. The shaft power is evaluated with Eq. (1). The parameters describing the windplanes and the quantities of the isolated upwind system are given in Table 1.

Table 1: Main parameters for the windplanes and optimal quantities of the upwind system.

		Description			Description
b	30 m	Wing span	C_P	0.98	Power coefficient
\mathcal{R}	6	Aspect ratio (elliptic)	C_T	2.91	Thrust coefficient
airfoil	NACA4421	Wing airfoil	λ	7.39	Wing speed ratio
R_t	3 m	Onboard turbines radius	κ_0	0.15	Inverse turning ratio
$C_{d,te}$	0.8	Tether drag coefficient	R_0	97 m	Turning radius
L_{te}	450 m	Tether length	a_t	0.032	Onboard turbines induction
D_{te}	30 mm	Tether diameter	C_L	1.00	Wing lift coefficient
m	2000 kg	Mass	a_f	0.043	Far wake induction

Referring to Fig. 4, we consider three cases for the downwind system, whose ground station is placed at one tether length L_{te} along the wind direction. In case (a), the two trajectories are concentric. In case (b), the downwind windplane has a ground station displaced laterally of Δy compared to the upwind system. In case (c), the trajectory of the second system is yawed of γ with respect to the incoming wind speed direction.

Fig. 5 shows the optimal trajectories for case (a). Two local optima are found for the downwind system: with smaller (\mathbf{dn}_{in}) and larger (\mathbf{dn}_{out}) turning radii. The turning radius is function of the wing lift coefficient C_L via Eq. (9), which is a control variable. Table 2 shows the local optima characteristics, with a significant reduction in power production of the downwind

Figure 4: Graphical representation of the considered cases for the sensitivity analysis. Case (a) represents two systems aligned with the wind direction and operated to have concentric trajectories. Case (b) represents two systems where the downwind system is displaced laterally with respect to the wind direction of Δy . Case (c) represents two systems aligned with the wind direction where the downwind system is operated with a yaw angle γ .

systems. The downwind windplane operated with lower lift coefficient, and thus with larger turning radius, achieves higher power production.

Figure 5: Trajectories of the upwind system **up** and of the optimal control strategies for the downwind system **dn**.

	up	dn_{out}	dn_{in}	
P	868	587	508	kW
P/P_{up}	1	0.68	0.58	-
L	323	231	227	kN
L/L_{up}	1	0.71	0.70	-
a_w	0	0.05	0.14	-
u	59.2	63.7	44.1	m/s
κ_0	0.15	0.12	0.17	-
R_0	97	122	87	m
a_t	0.032	0.017	0.047	-
C_L	1.00	0.63	1.27	-

Table 2: Key performance quantities for the two optimal control strategies of the downwind system **dn** at $v_\infty = 8$.

Concerning case **(b)** of Fig. 4, the power of the downwind system, normalized with the upwind system power, as a function of the lateral displacement is shown in Fig. 6a. Fig. 6b shows the power of the downwind system, normalized with the upwind system power, as a function of the yaw angle of the downwind system (case **(c)** of Fig. 4). For $\Delta y = 0$ and $\gamma = 0$, the solution coincides with the **dn_{out}** in Table 2. For large values of Δy and γ , the downwind system does not feel anymore the upwind system influence. In case **(b)** the power gets to the maximum value, while in case **(c)** the power is limited by the cosine-cubed losses. Indeed, as the system operated with an angle γ with respect to the wind direction, the maximum power decrease with the $\cos(\gamma)^3$. Both trends present a local maximum, which is of interest for wind farm layout optimization and control. Fig. 6b shows also the normalized power obtained in case **(b)** $P_{dn}(\Delta y)$ (Fig. 6a) multiplied by $\cos(\gamma_y)^3$, where $\gamma_y = \arctan\left(\frac{\Delta y}{L_{te}}\right)$. The almost perfect match between the two normalized powers curves shows that the two physical effects determining the curve $P_{dn}(\gamma)$ are the displacement of the trajectory center ($P_{dn}(\Delta y)$) and the yawing of the trajectory with respect to the wind (γ). The local maximum in case **(c)** shows a significant increase in power output of approx 15% with respect to the nominal case.

In case **(b)** the local maximum is $P_{dn}/P_{up} = 0.92$, found at $\Delta y^* = 135$ m, with $a_t = 0.031$

Figure 6: Power of the downwind system, normalized with the upwind system power, as a function of the lateral displacement Δy , normalized with the upwind system turbine radius **(a)** and as a function of the yaw angle of the downwind system γ **(b)**.

and $C_L = 0.98$. In case (c) the global maximum is $P_{dn}/P_{up} = 0.85$, found at $\gamma^* = 10^\circ$, with $a_t = 0.031$ and $C_L = 0.99$. The two ensuing trajectories are shown in Fig. 7a. The analyzed optima are characterized by an intersection of the projection of two trajectories. In this way, the downwind system makes use of high wind speed region in the core region of the wake. Fig. 7b shows the incoming wind speed perpendicular to the trajectory plane, showing a decrease in wind speed corresponding to the intersection with the projection of the upwind system trajectory.

Figure 7: Trajectories (a) and incoming wind speed perpendicular to the trajectory plane (b) of the local optima for case (b) and (c).

Fig. 8a shows the windplane tangential velocity, which decreases when the wind speed drops due to the upwind system wake. Note that the control inputs (lift coefficient C_L and turbine induction a_t) are optimized to a constant over the loop. Finally, Fig. 8b shows the shaft power over the loop for the three systems.

Figure 8: Tangential windplane speed u (a) and shaft power P (b) of the local optima for case (b) and (c).

6. Conclusions

The aerodynamic interaction between two fly-gen Airborne Wind Energy Systems, called windplanes in this paper, is studied with a new Gaussian wake model. The engineering wake models of windplanes can be split in induction models, used to find the induced velocities at the wing, and wake models, used to model the wind deficit after the wing. The induction model is taken from literature, it is based on vortex rings and the model used to find the vortex rings convection velocity is compared with results from vortex particle method simulations. A new

wake model is derived, assuming that the wake velocity has a Gaussian shape and respects the momentum conservation in the wake. The variance of the Gaussian wake is assumed to vary with the downstream distance and one tuning parameter is fitted to CFD results available in the literature. This wake model needs to be validated and tuned with more CFD analyses and experiments in the future and extended to more realistic cases of windplanes flying with an elevation angle above the ground. Later, the aerodynamic influence of an upwind system on a downwind system is studied with a sensitivity analysis, where the downwind system is moved in the direction transverse to the wind speed or it is operated with a yaw angle with respect to the wind direction. A maximum in power production of the downwind system is found when the projections of the two trajectories are partially overlapping. The extremely low computational cost of the model and the physical insights provided in the text contribute to clear the way for simulation, planning and control of large scale airborne wind farms.

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